

LIGHTWEIGHT DESIGN OF BATTERY BOX FOR ELECTRIC VEHICLE

Zhao Xiaoyu¹, Zhang Boming², Zhang Shuren³

1. College of Mechanical and Electric Engineering, Changchun University of science and technology,
Changchun 130022 China, xyzhao875@163.com

2. School of Materials Science and Engineering, Beihang University, Beijing, 100191 China,
738164370@qq.com

3. College of Mechanical and Electric Engineering, Changchun University of science and technology,
Changchun 130022 China, srzhang@163.com

Keywords: Composite plates, Battery box, Dynamic and static analysis, Morphology optimization

ABSTRACT

Aiming to the lightweight design of the battery box for electric vehicle, this paper research the design process and the strength analysis method of long carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic (LCFT) for a battery box of a sanitation vehicle. First, the box's basal body structure is obtained base on static loading state, the safety margin optimization is conducted to structure the lightest weight and highest performance laminated plates. Second, building strengthen structure in order to improve the ability of under dynamic load, as the unexpected situations may happen when driving a vehicle, such as frontal impact, side impact, dropping collision, and the robust structure of box with reinforcing rib of the long carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic (LCFT) is obtained. In order to check the safety performance of the battery box under static or dynamic loads, by using ABAQUS finite element software. Third, to avoid the resonance with chassis parts by using topography optimization method, optimization results show that the improved structure not only satisfy the requirement of the dynamic and static load bearing and inherent frequency. The lifting lug of metallic insert molded-in is another typical feature in order to improve connection stiffness for box. The analysis results show that the battery box saves about 42% weight compared to the aluminum alloy. The methods and consideration in this paper may also provide some ways to design and strength analysis for composite material components that meet the requirement of automotive lightweight.

1 INTRODUCTION

Battery box is a container of battery in the electric vehicles, which plays an important role in protecting the battery [1]. A group of battery boxes that fixed in carriage for electric vehicle. In order to carry loading of battery, the metallic material is used to be selected. Table 1 is a metallic material property which is adopted firstly. Every battery box loading is 201.6kg. Figure 1 is the assembly model of battery box.

E (MPa)	μ	$\rho(\text{g/cm}^3)$	$\sigma_s(\text{MPa})$	$\sigma_b(\text{MPa})$
2.1×10^5	0.3	7.8	210	270

Table 1: Metallic material attribute

The thickness of the side body of the metallic box is 2mm, the thickness of bottom of the metallic box is 3mm. The strength for loading the battery is satisfied by the finite element analysis, but the heavy of each box is 41.2kg, so the box's weight should be reduced for improving the battery efficiency. Therefore, the composite material is applied to reduce the battery box weight and improve its stiffness, because the composite material has high specific strength and large specific modulus.

Figure 1: Assembly model of battery box

2. STATIC ANALYSIS AND BASEBOARD STRUCTURE DESIGN

According analysis situation of the battery loading know that the static pressure is uniformly distributed load, so to apply the composite material design ways, the cross-sectional plies of basal board structure is (0/-45/90/45/90/-45/0/45)s, (s=2). The reinforce fiber is carbon fiber T300, the matrix is resin 5208. Table 1 is material properties of T300 /5208.

composit material	v_f	P (Kg/m ³)	E ₁ /GPa	E ₂ /GPa	ν_1 /GPa	F ₁₁ /GPa	F ₂₂ /GPa	F ₁₂ /GPa	F ₆₆ /GPa	F ₁ /GPa	F ₂ /GPa
carbon/ resin T300/5208	0.7	1600	181	10.3	0.28	0.444	101.6	-3.36	216.2	0	20.93

Table 2: Material properties of T300 /5208

Apply ABAQUS software analysis that basal structure of box[2]. Fig.2 show the result of analysis.

(a) σ_1 stress clouds

(b) σ_2 stress clouds

(c) τ_{12} stress clouds

Figure 2: $\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \tau_{12}$ stress clouds of composite battery box

Form the results have knew that the stresses, so apply the Tsai-Wu tensor criterion to calculate box's strength:

$$f(\sigma) = F_{11}\sigma_1^2 + 2F_{12}\sigma_1\sigma_2 + F_{22}\sigma_2^2 + F_{66}\tau_{12}^2 + F_1\sigma_1 + F_2\sigma_2 = 0.89 < 1 \quad (1)$$

Check results show that the floor can be within the scope of the safety margin under static load. The safety margin optimization is conducted to structure the lightest weight and highest performance laminated plates.

3. DYNAMIC LOADING ANALYSIS

The battery boxes not only carry the battery in the static situation but also bear the dynamic loading, such as vibrate, emergency brake, make a turn etc., so the basal box need reinforcing rid to benefit the strength. To apply OptiStruct modules of HyperWorks optimize the structure of the battery box, Figure 3 show the optimization result of box's morphology[3].

Figure3: Optimization results of battery box morphology

Based on the results of shape optimization and considering the requirements of production process, the battery box bottom of reinforced structure is modified, the really box model is showed in Figure 4. In addition to consider the strength of the battery box design also need to consider its natural vibration frequency.

Figure 4: Battery box reinforced rib structure

4. STRUCTURAL MODAL ANALYSIS.

In order to avoid the box will resonance with the chassis components. At the same time of increase box's stiffness and increase the inherent frequency of the box. Figure 5 show the modal analysis after reinforced rib structure.

Figure 5: One to six vibration model of composite battery box

By the analysis and calculation, the new battery box one to six order natural frequency values and resonance position as shown in Tab.3 The vibration frequency obviously have been improved.

degree	Frequency [HZ]	Vibration area
1	60.504	cover
2	84.130	baseboard
3	96.212	cover
4	141.63	baseboard、flank
5	144.93	baseboard、flank
6	153.71	cover

Table. 3: Natural frequency of composite battery box

5. DYNAMIC LOADING ANALYSIS FOR LIFTING LUG

The product process is difference between the meallc material and composite material, the lifting lug will be wedding with the box body if the material is metal, but the lifting lug with composite material that will be integrated forming. So, in order to improve the jointed strength, the lifting lug connect to the box body need bigger common area, the structure of lifting lug is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Battery box lifting lug

Figure7: Stress cloud of the lifting lug

The lifting lug operatively connected to the supporter by blot, the ply structure of connecting area where fastening to the supporter is $(0/-45/90/45/90/-45/0/45)_s$ ($s=4$), the lug strength should be designed enough to withstand the effects of the inertia force from time to time, the stress value around the bolt hole should be less than the ultimate strength of composite material, the thickness of lifting lug can check with finite element analysis[4], the figure 7 show the stress cloud of the lifting lug. The lifting lug of metallic insert molded-in is another typical feature in order to improve connection stiffness for box.

6. METAL MATERIALS AND COMPOSITE MATERIALS BATTERY BOX PERFORMANCE COMPARISON

In order to check whether the battery box designed meet the design purpose , Metal materials and composite materials battery box performance comparison is shown in Table.3, the result shown that the weight reduce about 42%.

material	aluminum alloy	basal body of box	box with rib
maximum static stress [MPa]	85.45	86.20	77.12
maximum deformation [mm]	0.98	1.09	0.76
baseboard thickness [mm]	3	3.2	3.2
lateral thickness around [mm]	2	2	2
quality of battery box[Kg]	41.2	22	23.8

Table 4: Comparison of three kinds of battery box

7. CONCLUSION

Battery box security and economy is an important indicator of design and fabrication. Traditional battery box with aluminum casting mode made the vehicle heavy and process complicated. In order to protect the environment and reserve energy, the development of automotive industry more and more light weight and low-cost. Advanced reinforced resin matrix composites have advantages of low density, high strength modulus, corrosion-resistant, and integrated manufacture, so the metallic battery box will be replaced.

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